

Designing a 3D model of a modular house

Today, modular construction is becoming more and more popular due to its speed, economy and adaptability to modern needs.

Today, modular construction is becoming popular due to the growing demands for environmental responsibility and energy efficiency.

Thanks to the modular design, quick and efficient construction of the house is ensured, which significantly shortens the construction period. Environmentally friendly materials minimize the impact on the environment, and a well-thought-out ventilation system creates a comfortable microclimate for residents. Such a house meets modern requirements for the quality of life, maintaining a balance between innovation and care for nature.

Modular houses allow you to create quickly erected, energy-efficient and environmentally friendly structures that meet modern requirements for sustainable development.

An eco-house built using such materials has numerous advantages in terms of environmental friendliness, energy efficiency and sustainability.

The work solves a complex of important tasks aimed at developing an effective solution for the construction of modular houses. 3D models of the building were created, with the help of which it is possible to evaluate the rationality of the use of materials, and an analysis of the strength of the building and the load was carried out using the modern Autodesk Fusion 360 software.

The purpose of the work is to develop a house assembled from modules. The dimensions of such a house are 10 by 10 meters, the area is 100 m².

Designing begins with determining the dimensions of the house and its functional areas. Modules of 5 by 5 meters were chosen, the size of the house 10 by 10 meters allows to place two rooms, a bathroom, a kitchen and other necessary spaces.

At the sketch design stage, conceptual versions of the house are developed, which allows you to see how the main functional areas may look and how the spaces

within the building will be organized. This makes it possible to choose the most suitable plan and structure that takes into account the needs of residents and allows efficient use of space.

Creating a mock-up helps to visualize and evaluate the project in real size or scale, which allows you to see how the elements of the building will look and how they interact. This is an important stage for identifying flaws and inaccuracies at an early stage to avoid mistakes in future construction.

At the stage of creating a 3D model, the house is transferred into digital form, which allows you to accurately check the dimensions, structural solutions, as well as calculate how all the elements of the building will interact. This allows you to correct possible shortcomings and optimize the structure at the construction stage, which significantly reduces the probability of errors during the execution of work.

Modeling allows you to visualize the structure of the building, identify possible structural problems and optimize the use of materials. Thanks to such a model, it is possible to more accurately predict what the finished house will look like and how various engineering systems (water supply, heating, ventilation) will work.

The sketch design stage helps to optimize the internal planning, and the creation of a 3D model provides an opportunity to check the design and identify implementation errors. The layout of the house allows you to visualize the result and test the solution in practice.

Project virtualization through 3D modeling is one of the key stages that allows you to check all project solutions in digital format. This ensures the accuracy of calculations, the detection of structural construction errors, as well as the ability to make corrections to the project based on real data.

Modeling in Fusion 360 is the process of creating digital 3D models of objects and structures, which is carried out using Autodesk Fusion 360 software. It is a powerful tool for design, modeling, simulations and manufacturing that combines several stages of development, such as CAD - Computer-Aided Design, CAM - Computer-Aided Manufacturing, CAE - Computer-Aided Engineering, as well as real-time collaboration.

Fusion 360 allows you to work with different types of models, combining all stages - from design to production - in one environment. This significantly reduces time and increases the accuracy of work.

Fusion 360 enables you to create complex 3D models with millimeter accuracy, allowing you to build accurate designs for manufacturing, design verification, and visualization. This enables prototyping without the need for physical fabrication.

These advantages make Fusion 360 a powerful and versatile tool for a variety of projects, from mechanical design to architectural solutions, including modular home design.

Modeling in Fusion 360 for the project of a modular eco-house made of environmentally friendly nanomaterials can be done in several main stages.

At the beginning, it is necessary to clearly define all the requirements for the house model: dimensions, structure, functionality and type of materials. This includes planning the main parts of the building such as walls, roofs, doors, windows and other important components. After that, all the necessary information is collected regarding the dimensions and characteristics of materials for

Figure 1 – Creation of the first and second row of nanobricks

Copy the two rows of soil blocks using the "Rectangular Pattern" command as many times as necessary to reach the height of the building. To create the texture of

nanobricks and determine their properties, we use the "Appearance" command, which is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Creating a building and providing an invoice to the materials

When the nanobrick module is built, we create an imitation of a nanoconcrete solution by sketching a rectangle in the shape of the building and extruding it with the "Extrude" command and cutting it to the shape of a nanobrick using "Combine", which is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Creating a texture for nanoconcrete materials.

Figure 4 shows a 3D model of a house consisting of 4 modules. Use the Extrude and Rectangular Pattern commands to create room dividers and 900mm cutouts for doors. Openings for windows and doors are made according to the same principle.

Figure 4 – 3D model of the building

To build the roof, we create a sketch of the beam and add the width of the pipe using the "Extrude" functions. The finished result is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Construction of the roof

After the construction of the roof base, you can see the created 3D model, shown in Figure 5, made in Autodesk Fusion software.